

IMPACT OF NEW EDUCATION POLICY ON EDUCATION FIELD

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Abstract

New education policy 2020 great impact on current education. Teacher education programmes in professional education, at college and university level, tend to have a wide scope of objective. These need to be focused and teachers need to be educated to specialize in teaching particular subjects. A heavy dependence on the individual understanding of teachers and their ability to evolve teaching methods leads not only to highly varying outcomes in students, but also puts undue pressure on teachers. Collaborative and experiential learning methods and an awareness of professional ethics need to be brought in systematically through improved teacher education from new education policy. NEP is basically a comprehensive framework to guide the development of current education in the country. Indian government decided to revise 1968, 1986 and 1992 policies to make them more relevant and compelling for the education ecosystem in NEP 2020.

Introduction

NEP 2020 has impacted school, college education and teacher education equally; and the effects will surreal with great level change in higher education. NEP 2020 is proposal to setup the higher education commission of India (HECI), a single overarching umbrella body for higher education, including medical and legal education. HECI has four independent vertical's – National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) for regulation., General Education Council (GEC) for standard-setting, Higher Education Grants Council (HEGC) for funding and National Accreditation Council (NAC) for accreditation. In a country, to have uniformity in education standards, a single umbrella body was always a requirement. Multiple independent governing bodies led to many standardization issues across institution, and along with that, any improvement plan to be implemented in this higher education domain took years. If the proposed plan to be implemented, uniformity and coordination for

all institutions in this country will be much easier. Process changes will be easily implemented and effective too.

Professional education continues to be a domain where teachers are still largely Master's degree holders and likely to continue to remain so in the foreseeable future. Professional education is also an area in which people with industry/ business/ hospital experience must be invited to come back and teach with appropriate preparation. It must be ensured that new faculty receive induction training and continuous in-service professional development for current education system.

NEP 2020 great impact on current education system like -

1) NEP 2020 Proposal a single university entrance exam conducted by National Testing Agency :

NTA conduct university examination varied difficulty level of question papers across many central universities and the admission process will be streamlined.

2) Setting up Departments of Education for preparing faculty for professional education :

In order to strengthen teacher education in the professional education steams, Departments of Education will be set up, if they don't already exist, at all universities that affiliate colleges offering professional education in any discipline. It is expected that these universities will eventually evolve into multidisciplinary HEIs. These Departments of Education will develop curriculum for teacher education in the respective profession and offer the Master's degree in Teaching and Research, which will be a mandatory qualification for all aspiring teachers, to be taken besides a Master's degree in their subject specialization. The course will orient aspiring teachers and practitioners on curriculum development, pedagogy, assessment techniques etc., and will be delivered in the part-time, blended, or online mode to enable access to working professionals.

3) Mitigating the shortage of faculty across disciplines:

Universities and institution will be encouraged and facilitated to address faculty shortage in multiple ways: taking measures to attract and retain faculty; engaging with other institutions in the vicinity to share faculty; inviting rolling faculty of eminent and superannuated scientists'/professors'/ experts from industry; talent from the private sector; inviting overseas researches etc.

3) Professional development of faculty:

The Departments of Education at the for the professional development of faculty. Research will not be mandatory for all teachers in the shorter run, and emphasis will be shifted towards teaching methodology, classroom innovations and student motivation in evaluating teachers. Writing of textbooks, and translation of literature between different languages also support and encouragement.

4) Research:

Research in all professional disciplines will be eligible for funding by the NRF. Existing funding agencies such as the ICMR and the ICAR will also knowledge generation as well as towards improving the outcomes of professional education. At the National level, it shall provide the basis for policy making and perspective planning, including facilitating decisions around setting up new institutions. At the institutional level, it will facilitate curricular and pedagogical improvement.

5) In service professional development:

Professional education continues to be a domain where teachers are still largely Master's degree holders and likely to continue to remain so in the foreseeable future. Professional education is also an area in which people with industry/ business/ hospital experience must be invited to come back and teach with appropriate preparation. It must ne ensured that new faculty receive induction training and continuous in-service professional development.

6) Professional Councils for Teachers:

A professional council for faculty in each discipline of professional education is necessary, to take responsibility for ensuring that every faculty member receives refresher courses at regular intervals. For instance, a professional body for teachers at medical colleges will be created so that teachers can upgrade their knowledge every five years. Infrastructure for providing continuing education in all branches of medicine, including nursing, dental and allied health, will be strengthened for this purpose.

• Summary

Post-graduate education in the professional streams need to be strengthened considerably. The curriculum must ensure that post-graduates acquire knowledge, skills, self-confidence and entrepreneurship training, to enable them to contribute to social and national productivity.

Post- graduates either go on to professional practice at higher levels or become educated by taking up teaching, with only a very small fraction continuing into research. In either case, they need to be among the best possible education. The new NEP 2020 suggested changes look great on paper and they would change the face of Indian Current Education System in the years to come, but that would depend on how they – teachers, institution, leadership and governance are approached and implemented.

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